

Current Trends in Digital Marketing: A Study on Odisha

Seema Rani Giri, Assistant Professor
Dr.Bhabani Shankar Dash, Associate Professor
(Dr.Ambedkar Memorial Institute of IT & Mgmt. Sc)

Abstract:- This article is aimed at the study of the growing revolution in digital marketing. In today's business environment digital marketing has taken a vast area. Digital marketing has a wider scope as the pace of technology is rapidly moving forward. Many companies are transforming their activities with the help of digital marketing. Companies are enriching their products in the digital arena and also marketing strategies are being adopted to the reach the target customer. Social media is playing a vital role in this concern. The research was been done during pandemic and it was found people are very convenient to purchase the product by using digital platform. As many of the shopping centers were closed people starting using online purchase. Companies have developed many Apps which helps the customer to browse easily and find products and order utilities through the respective Apps. The article throws light on the current trends of digital marketing in broader sense. The traditional and digital marketing differences are tried to show in this paper through a small research. The study is performed within Odisha. As the world has already entered into epoch of technology, the digital channel plays vital role in proliferation of sales of any firm's product.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Marketing refers to use of electronic media to reach out to customers in order to promote items. It also connects people and help to promote products via information sharing websites. It has become a globally popular trending sector. It is crossing milestone regularly with eachand every single day. It is wavering and thriving continuously and having a great pecuniary influence on the business.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sanjay Bhayani & Nishant V. Vachhan (2018) In this paper they have recognized the Internet and Traditional marketing strategies opinions. Consumers are more convenient in using internet facility now-a-days and it is available all 24 Hours. The consumers are becoming internet savvy and they have many purchasing options and preferences.

S. Sivasankaran (2017) in this paper he has marked upon many challenges in the retail segment of the market. The current generation has more fascination towards online shopping than offline buying. The digital marketing has

focused to use the innovative way and has pressurized the todays generation buying pattern. The buying pattern of the younger generation has a greater influence in buying behavior.

P.Sathya (2017) has studied about the avenue of electronic communication which the marketers have used to transfer the services and goods to the market. The purpose of Digital Marketing has concern to allow the customers to intermingle the product with the virtue of media.

D.M. Arvind& Shankar Narayan Rao (2017) this paper has researched about Digital Marketing , that it has created an enormous buzz in Digital Marketing. It has focused in younger, middle and the older generation. This paper had thrown light on various aspects of Digital Marketing, to keep the consumers more digitalized. The research also shows the future scenario with younger generation which identifies the growth and size in current perspective.

Mr. Rajiv Kaushiv, 'Digital Marketing in Indian Context,' (2016) Digital marketing is rising in India with fast pace. Many Indian companies are using digital marketing for competitive advantage. Success of marketing campaign cannot be solely achieved by digital marketing only.

Mr. Yasmin, Mrs. Tasneem in his paper 'Effectiveness of Digital Marketing in the Challenging Age' (2015) discussed that Marketers are faced with new challenges and opportunities within this digital age. Digital Marketing is the use of electronic media by the advertisers to advance the items or administrations into the market.

III. STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Marketers needs to find out whether to communicate with the audience in Online Mode or Offline mode? As nowadays people are more savvy with digital platforms.

A. Research Objective:

- To understand consumer awareness regarding digital marketing
- To analyze how Digital Marketing plays a significant role among people of Odisha

B. Research Design

Here , the population is from different places of Odisha and information has been gathered from the respondents to finish the study. Random Sampling has been used to gather the information from the sample.

C. Sources of Data Collection

Here , the data has been collected from both Primary and Secondary source. Through Google form the Questionnaire has been circulated among the different

places of Odisha. 106 individuals has given their views in the Questionnaire.

The questionnaire was prepared in a view to get detail information about the study. Different age groups preferences has been gathered. In this study , secondary data has been collected from various modes such as Internet Websites, Reports of research scholars, journals , books etc..

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Graph No-1. Graph showing gender distribution in the sample

Graph No-2. Graph showing age distribution in the sample

Graph No-3. Graph showing educational qualification distribution in the sample

ARE YOU AWARE ABOUT DIGITAL MARKETING ?

106 responses

Graph No-4 Graph showing awareness about Digital Marketing distribution in the sample

DO YOU EVER PURCHASE ONLINE ?

106 responses

Graph No-5 Graph showing online purchasing distribution in the sample

IF YES, WHAT TYPE OF PRODUCT/SERVICE YOU PURCHASE ONLINE?

106 responses

Graph No-6 Graph showing type of product/service purchase online distribution in the sample

ARE YOU SATISFIED WITH THE PRODUCT BOUGHT USING DIGITAL PLATFORM ?

106 responses

Graph No-7 Graph showing satisfaction with the product bought using Digital Platform distribution in the sample

HOW OFTEN YOU BUY PRODUCTS USING DIGITAL PLATFORM ?

106 responses

Graph No-8 Graph showing product bought using digital platform distribution in the sample

DO YOU THINK DIGITAL MARKETING IS THE BEST PLATFORM TO BUY THE PRODUCTS ?

106 responses

Graph No-9 Graph showing digital marketing is the best platform to buy the product distribution in the sample

WHY DO YOU GO FOR DIGITAL PLATFORM TO PURCHASE PRODUCTS ?

106 responses

Graph No-10 Graph showing digital platform to purchase products distribution in the sample

ARE YOU SATISFIED WITH THE QUALITY AFTER PURCHASING THE PRODUCT THROUGH DIGITAL PLATFORM ?

106 responses

Graph No-11 Graph showing satisfaction with the quality after purchasing the product distribution in the sample

WHAT BENEFITS DOES ONLINE MARKETING OFFER OVER TRADITIONAL MARKETING?

106 responses

Graph No-12 Graph showing benefits of Online marketing over traditional marketing

RATE ONLINE MARKETING

106 responses

Graph No-13 Graph showing ratings on Online marketing distribution in the sample**V. OBSERVATION**

From the data collected it is been interpreted that out of 106 respondents 83% are aware about Digital marketing and 96% people purchase online using digital platform. It is also found from the information that 67% of the sample electronics products are more preferred to be purchased online. And 75% respondents are satisfied by the products bought using digital platform.

As per satisfaction percentage 64% of the respondents think marketing is the best platform to buy the product. As 79% respondents say its time saving. 72% of the total respondents are satisfied with the quality of the product.

52% of the Respondents have also marked 4 ratings out of 5 for online marketing.

VI. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study has been conducted purely based on primary data which has been collected through Questionnaire. The sample size for the study was limited to 106 respondents. Many of the people haven't responded the questionnaire send to them.

VII. CONCLUSION

Digital marketing as entered in the scenario it has come intriguing issue for the state. In this modern generation people want everything in their doorstep with a single click. They are using frequently to buy products using digital platform. Many apps have come up and its easy to install and people by sitting at home can go for digital marketing. Through this study it is found that teenagers are frequently go for digital marketing.

Moreover , digital marketing is the best platform as because product can be advertised easily. People life becomes easier with the pace of time as well as technology.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Rekha Chouhan, Mahima Singh, A study on Emerging Trends in Digital Marketing, 2021
- [2.] Archana Jain a , Varsha Srivastava, An Empirical Study on Digital Marketing, 2021 JETIR August 2021, Volume 8, Issue 8,
- [3.] Dr. Amit Singh Rathore , Mr.Mohit Pant , Mr.Chetan Sharma EMERGING TRENDS IN DIGITAL MARKETING IN INDIA,
- [4.] Shreya Verma , Dr. Umesh Chandra DIGITAL MARKETING AND ITS CURRENT TRENDS: A CASE STUDY OF BUXAR (BIHAR) International Journal of Innovative Research in Management Studies (IJIRMS) Volume 5, Issue 5, May 2021. pp.6-12.
- [5.] Kotler, Philip. Marketing management/Philip Kotler, Kevin Lane Keller. — 14th ed. publishing as Prentice Hall, One Lake Street, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey 07458
- [6.] G. NEDUMARAN(2016), 'Digital Marketing trends in India,' International Journal of Advanced Scientific Research & Development, Vol. 03, Issue 01, ISSN : 2395-6089 (Online), ISSN : 2394-8906 (Print).
- [7.] UDIT AGARWAL , DR. RAJESH VERMA Emerging Trends in Digital Marketing, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET) e-ISSN: 2395-0056 Volume: 06 Issue: 05 | May 2019 www.irjet.net p-ISSN: 2395-0072 © 2019, IRJET | Impact Factor value: 7.211 | ISO 9001:2008 Certified Journal | Page 535
- [8.] A Munshi, MSS MUNSHI (2012), "Digital marketing: A new buzz word", International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research, Vol.2 Issue 7.
- [9.] Dr.R.Venkatamuni Reddy Professor and Head Digital Marketing: Current Trends in India National Conference On 'Emerging Trends In Information Technology In Today's Business Scenario' Organized By The Koshys Institute Of Management Studies, Bengaluru, India Held on 6th October 2016. Page 1 of 7